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**Characterization of e-sails: a novel propulsive
concept that exploits the solar wind to propel
larger spacecraft for interplanetary travel**

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Abstract

Pekka Janhunen of the Finnish Meteorological Institute first proposed the concept of electric sails in 2006, which utilize the solar wind dynamic pressure to generate a small, yet continuous thrust by interacting with an electric field generated from charged tethers. This technology could be a competitive propulsion system for future missions, and NASA's Marshall Space Center has provided funding for a Small Business Technology Transfer Phase II project to model the thruster performance of an E-sail spacecraft. This work will include a test campaign to validate parallel 3D Particle-In-Cell (PIC) codes with improved boundary conditions. This dissertation entails the experimental test campaign needed to validate the parallel 3D Particle-In-Cell (PIC) codes with improved boundary conditions. This campaign will be focused on characterizing the performances of a surrogate sail exposed to a high density, high velocity plasma stream simulating the solar wind, exploiting novel plasma accelerators. To better estimate the power consumption required for keeping the tethers at high potential the current discharge will be investigated. Estimating the momentum poses challenges, in particular devising a thrust measurement technique that allows for high sensitivity. Upon successful completion of the Phase II effort, the validated PIC-based approaches will be used to examine the controllability and optimization of E-sail spacecraft, including its size and layout, as well as adapting it to the changing plasma environment for in-space operations.

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Nomenclature

ϵ_0	First ionization energy
μ_0	Magnetic permittivity of vacuum
ϕ	Plasma potential
B	Magnetic field
E	Electric field
e	Electrons
i	Ions
k_b	Boltzmann constant
l	Degrees of freedom
n	Volumetric particle density
q	Electron charge
S_i	Mach number relative to ion acoustic speed
V	Potential

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation and background

In 2006, Dr. Pekka Janhunen of the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) developed the electric sail at the Kumpula Space Centre in Finland. Since then, Dr. Janhunen has conducted extensive research and published numerous works on this form of propulsion.[15] The HERTS propulsion system is based on the exchange of momentum between an "electric sail" and the solar wind. The electric sail consists of a number of long, charged wires that extend 10 to 30 km from a slowly rotating spacecraft. A high voltage potential is applied to the wires to deflect the positively charged solar wind protons and transfer momentum from the solar wind to the array. Solar wind speeds typically range from 300 to 700 km/s and flow radially away from the sun. The 2013 MSFC Advanced Concepts Office (ACO) conducted a high-level feasibility study that showed a HERTS propulsion system could potentially propel a spacecraft to speeds up to three to four times faster than what could be achieved with solar electric or solar sail propulsion systems.

The National Research Council's Solar and Space Physics 2013 Heliophysics Decadal Survey has provided the impetus for the development of a revolutionary propulsion technology. Section 10.5.2.7 of the survey states that the Interstellar Probe Mission would involve comprehensive, state-of-the-art in-situ measurements for understanding the outer heliosphere and exploring our local galactic environment. It further emphasizes the need for advanced propulsion options that could reach the heliopause faster than Voyager 1 (3.6 AU/year). The Solar and Heliospheric Physics (SHP) Panel has placed a high priority on NASA developing the required propulsion technology for ambitious missions such as The Solar Polar Imager (SPI) and Interstellar Probe in the near future. In 2013 the ESTCube-1, the first

Figure 1.1: Image shown is copyright by: Alexandre Szames, Antigravite, Paris.

Estonian satellite, was launched. ESTCube-1 had the objective to deploy and power up a 10 m tether and observe the variations in the satellite's spin rate [17].

These alterations are caused by the Coulomb drag interaction with the ionospheric plasma that is in motion relative to the satellite as a result of its orbital motion. Unfortunately, the deployment mechanism didn't manage to survive the launcher vibrations, and thus no measures were collected [16].

In 2018 Bruce M. Wiegmann from NASA MSFC proposed a technology demonstration mission: the selected architecture consists of two 6U Cubesats bonded with a 16 km long tether. The mission objectives were to deploy the tether, and measure the generated thrust.

Last, but not least, the idea of charged tethers can be more than just a propellant-less propulsion system. If charged negatively, it can act as a brake in the ionosphere, for satellite de-orbiting. If not charged, the resulting current can be exploited for energy generation purposes.

1.2 NASA MSFC E-sails test campaign

An experimental campaign for the E-sails was conducted in 2017 by the Space Environmental Effects Team at NASA Marshall Space Flight Center, in the HERTS laboratories. [4]

The team chose a Kaufman ion source to replicate the solar wind in a vacuum chamber; to understand why this may not be the best option in terms of accuracy, it can be useful to describe the architecture of this system.

Electrons emitted from a hot filament in the ionization chamber are accelerated to the anode, while a permanent magnet increases its path length as they spiral toward the anode, thereby increasing the efficiency of ionization of an inert gas such as argon. The screen grid, which contains the plasma, is floating and its potential is dependent on the plasma potential, which is determined by the discharge parameters. The ion current available from the ion source is determined by parameters including gas pressure, cathode power, anode potential, and geometry. The accelerator grid serves two purposes: extracting the ions from the discharge chamber and focusing the ions trajectories. A neutralizer, which is a hot filament supplying electrons, can be added to the system to neutralize the ions on their way to the sample. If the neutralizer current is equal to the ion current, the beam can be completely neutralized.

Figure 1.2: Scheme of a Kaufman ion acceleration facility.[14]

The resulting stream flux of plasma has an ionization degree far from the one of the solar wind, in which on the contrary the ionization fraction can reach 95%. The abundance of neutral particles,

therefore, makes the results of NASA MSFC not reliable for the scope of thrust determination.

Figure 1.3: Photograph of the Kaufman accelerator used at MSFC.

1.3 Research objectives

Stanford University together with NASA Marshall Space Center and Particle Matters under the STTR program is currently involved in understanding the potential of this very futuristic technology. The project, currently in the STTR Phase II aims to model and predict the performances of this novel propulsive concept using a high-fidelity computational approach. An experimental test campaign is needed to validate the parallel 3D Particle-In-Cell (PIC) codes with improved boundary conditions.

The experimental test campaign aims to address multiple research questions:

- Estimating the current discharged by a wire charged at a certain high potential to validate the respective PIC estimation. This value of current is fundamental to estimate the energy consumption of the propulsive unit since the potential of the wires will be higher than the plasma potential emitter has to expel electrons in the real spacecraft, and therefore it will demand energy from the electric power generators. The secondary objective of this measurement will be the testing and characterizing the dynamics of the test setup, which will be charged at a certain potential and tested in the subsequent experiment for current discharge measurements.
- Estimating the thrust generated by a charged wire in an accelerated and highly ionized plasma, together with the propulsive efficiency of the system. Once this part of the PIC code is validated it would also be possible to characterize the structure of the plasma around the wire, especially the plasma sheath radius and the trapped electrons orbiting around the wires.

The experimental setup will be scaled for practical reasons. Particularly the potential of the wires, which has to be reduced in the order of hundreds of volts and the length to the order of centimeters. Upon the success of the Phase II effort, the validated PIC-based approaches will be well suited to examine key issues of E-sails spacecraft controllability and optimization, including its size and layout, as well as adapting it to the changing plasma environment for in-space operations.

Chapter 2

E-sails comprehensive theory

2.1 E-sail concept introduction

The concept of solar sails that will be discussed in this dissertation and inspired this project has been invented by Prof. Pekka Janhunen in 2007. This cutting-edge propellantless propulsion system exploits the momentum flux of the solar wind, as a big sail made out of a set of thin long wires, charged at a high positive potential that allows them to repel protons and deflect the incident solar wind.

Onboard the spacecraft an electron gun would keep the wires at their potential, consuming electrical power. The efficiency of the system depends on the force exerted on a wire and the current drawn from the plasma that constitutes the solar wind. Assessing these two physical quantities can be challenging, but is fundamental to understand the power of this technology.

The solar wind dynamic pressure $\rho \cdot V^2$ is just about 2nPa at 1 AU; for this reason, the force per unit length on a single tether will be weak. Wires must be as thin as possible to reduce the mass, but very long at the same time to maximize the force generated. The absence of a propellant will make the spacecraft extremely light, especially in the case of long, interplanetary flight for which this technology is tailored to. Over a period of months, a spacecraft could be accelerated to enormous speeds of 100-150 km/s, reaching the heliosphere in a matter of 10 years, while the voyager mission took 37 years to reach the same distance.[4]

Generally speaking, in a realistic spacecraft, the applied potential could be in the order of 15-20 kV, around 100 wires in total each 10 km long, with a diameter of 25-50 μm , bonded in a Hoytether. The bonding possibility has been investigated by Pekka Jahumen in 2007. [6] The tethers will be

Figure 2.1: Particular of the Hoytether configuration, designed to the structural resistance.[5]

surrounded by a potential structure made out of electrons, whose density decreases with the distance from the tethers. Externally these electrons will be covered by protons, and they will generate a sheath around the tethers. With the plasma density at 1 AU being in the order of $7.3 \frac{1}{\text{cm}^3}$ the Debye length will be around 9m, and the effective "sheath width" of a charged tether will be a few times this quantity. The spacecraft will be spinning to maintain the tethers deployed for the effect of the centrifugal force. In principle, it will be also possible to control the attitude of this spacecraft by varying the potential applied to each singular tether, and generating a torque.

It has been shown that the force generated by a conventional solar sail, that exploits the radiation pressure, is dependent on the inverse square of the distance from the Sun. Several analytical estimations of the force show that this decays between $d^{-1.15}$ and d^{-1} . [6] This is advantageous for long-distance

Figure 2.2: Conceptual scheme of the electric sails.[6]

Figure 2.3: Starfish-like electrostatic potential structure around the charged tethers.[5]

interplanetary travel, and would drastically reduce the flight time with respect to a conventional solution.

The possibility of regulating the thrust is an additional advantage of this technology, considering that the solar wind is very variable in terms of density, speed, and temperature. On top of that, with respect to traditional electric propulsion architectures, the e-sails are propellantless, which leads to a drastic saving of fuel weight.

This dissertation will be focused on a testing campaign aimed to measure the thrust per length of a charged wire of a certain diameter. As stated before the e-sail project includes a myriad of challenges, from structural integration to robust attitude control strategies, which are out of the scope of this work.

2.2 Bi-dimensional theory for thrust calculations

Calculating the thrust generated by a fully three-dimensional structure can be very challenging and computationally very expensive; therefore engineers often simplify the problem in calculating the force per unit length ($\frac{dF}{dz}$) for a bi-dimensional cylindrical case.

Particle-in-cell simulations (PIC) are often employed for this purpose; they basically resolve partial differential equations in a Lagrangian frame to track individual particles, and eventually to compute densities, currents force, and torques.

Figure 2.4: Schematic view of E-sail with the remote unit and auxiliary tethers. The remote units are a possible solution for controlling the attitude and the spin rate of the spacecraft.[7]

Theoretical results are anyway essential to understand the physics behind these phenomena and predicting results for various plasma and wires properties since PIC simulations are computationally demanding.

From the Laplace theory, the potential function of an infinite-long wire can be derived.

$$V(r) = V_0 \frac{\ln(r_0/r)}{r_0/r_w} \quad (2.1)$$

where r_0 corresponds to the zero-potential radius for the symmetrical vacuum Laplace solution. [8] In reality around the wire electrons are present, and they make the potential vanish faster with respect to the vacuum solution. Janhunen et al. performed several PIC simulations and they derived this result:

$$V(r) = V_0 \frac{[1 + (r_0/r)^2]}{[1 + (r_0/r_w)^2]} \quad (2.2)$$

which takes into account the effect of the spatial charge around the wire.[6] However, the effect of the space charge may be assumed negligible. From the Gauss law it is possible to derive the electron distribution law:

$$n_e(r) = n_0 + \frac{\epsilon_0}{e} \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} (rV(r)) \quad (2.3)$$

This electron distribution surrounds the charged wires and it's in turn surrounded by protons eventually originating a sheath. The force per unit length can be calculated by multiplying the dynamic pressure by the radius of this sheath:

$$\frac{dF}{dz} = Km_p n R_s V^2 \quad (2.4)$$

where K is a constant that takes into account the variation between the analytic expression and the experimental results.

There are several methods to calculate the sheath radius. In 2007 Janhunen et al. computed this

quantity by assuming it was equal to the proton stopping distance. [6] Therefore, after equalizing the kinetic energy and the potential energy of a particle, the result is an equation that is solved for r , and a force gradient $F \sim \sqrt{(n_0 T_e)}$.

Another R_s estimation comes from Janhunen et al in 2009, in which the local electric pressure $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E^2$ balances the solar wind dynamic pressure. The result is dependent on the trapped electron density- i.e. the density of electrons that result to miss the wires but their kinetic energy is sufficient to orbit around them. The time before a collision can be estimated in the order of minutes [5] and obviously, a high electron density tends to decrease the maximum available amount of thrust since it shields partially the charged wires.

In 2008 Sanmartin et al.[8] determined the sheath thickness in an immobile, unmagnetized plasma:

$$1.53 \left[1 - 2.56 \frac{\lambda_{De}}{r_s} \right] \left(\frac{r_s}{\lambda_{De}} \right)^{\frac{4}{3}} \ln \left(\frac{r_s}{r_w} \right) = \frac{eV_0}{K_b T_e} \quad (2.5)$$

The radius computed from this equation is larger than the two previous methods and corresponds roughly to the distance where the potential energy is close to the electron temperature, expressed in electronvolts.

In the framework of this project, Prof. Ken Hara from Stanford Aero Astro and Dr. S. Gimelshein from ParticleMatters Inc. performed a series of simulations and found out that Sanmartin et al's radius with $K=0.25$ is the analytical estimation that best matches the PIC results, and hence it will be exploited for the calculations conducted in the design section of this dissertation. They also estimated a density of trapped electrons 200 times higher than the free-stream density, resulting in a force that is 2.5 times lower.

Figure 2.5: Plot of $\frac{dF}{dz}$ outside the terrestrial magnetosphere for a charged tether. At zero potential, the force is just the result of the dynamic pressure hitting the wires.

This solution can be acceptable for $V > 1$ kV. For a smaller voltage, it would overestimate the generated thrust since it overestimates the radius.

Figure 2.6: Plot of the Force gradient vs density.

The density is the leading parameter in the thrust determination, and thus critical in the testing campaign. A greater value of this physical quantity shows a smaller sheath radius since the Debye length decreases; however, what prevails is the contribution of the dynamic pressure that generates a greater thrust.

Figure 2.7: Results of the PIC simulations from Janhunen et al.[2]

The images presented above are the results of calculations for a wire of $10\mu\text{m}$ of radius charged at 5.6 kV right outside the magnetosphere (1AU). They show the structure of a bow-shock-like compression of ions around the wire, followed by strong rarefaction, as the repulsive potential of the is too high for a close approach.

2.3 Bi-dimensional theory for current calculations at spaceflight plasma density

It is important to know the electron current collected by the wire as it determines the current that the onboard electron gun must produce to maintain the desired positive potential of the wires. When the Debye length is greater than the cylinder radius, the Orbit Motion Limited (OML) theory is applicable, and will be the basis of the calculations in this section. In a stationary state, electrons that are held by the potential structure of the wire move without colliding with the wire, so only new electrons from the surrounding solar wind plasma contribute to the electron current. The orbits of these electrons depend only on the potential structure since the system is collisionless. Assuming there is no solar wind proton flow, making the situation cylindrically symmetric, the Coulomb force field acting on an incoming electron is a central force field, meaning the angular momentum and total energy of the particle are conserved. This makes it possible to calculate how accurately an incoming electron must be "aimed" to be in a collision course with the wire, and the result is independent of the functional form of the potential structure, only depending on the wire potential V_0 . [6] These assumptions state the Orbital Motion Limited theory which will be applied to the current calculations. This integral has to be solved:

$$i = 2\pi R_s L n q \int_0^{\text{inf}} \int_{-v_1}^{v_1} u F(u, v) du dv \quad (2.6)$$

with L being the probe length and

$$v_1 = \frac{r_w^2}{a^2 - r_w^2} \left(u^2 + 2 \frac{q}{m} V_0 \right) \quad (2.7)$$

To complete the calculation at this point it is necessary to assume a velocity distribution. [3] A Maxwellian distribution for a bi-dimensional velocity field will result in

$$f(u, v) = \frac{m}{2\pi k T} e^{-(m/2kT)(u^2+v^2)} \quad (2.8)$$

The assumption is valid just in equilibrium conditions. The final result for the current per length will be:

$$\frac{dI}{dz} = q n \sqrt{\frac{2qV_0}{m_e}} 2r_w \quad (2.9)$$

where $qV_0 \gg T_e$ since the wire will be charged at a potential in the order of kV. Following the Langmuir probe theory this formula is valid for positive currents far below the saturation value.

Physics tells us that the situation will be far from equilibrium, and hence it will be more opportune to compute the real velocity distribution function. This has been done through the PIC simulations.

Figure 2.8: Results of the current calculations for a wire at 1AU.

Figure 2.9: Ion and electron densities obtained for solar wind conditions at 1 AU.

The increase in electric current to the tether at a finite solar wind velocity is due to the compression of the plasma in front of the tether as a result of the large ion Mach number. This is illustrated in the figure above, where the ion and electron densities, normalized by the free stream value, are plotted along the symmetry axis. The tether is centered at $X=0$, and the plasma flow is from left to right. For the stagnant plasma (red lines), the ion density decreases to the tether, while the electron density follows the decrease in the ion density, and then sharply increases as the electrons are attracted by the high positive potential of the tether. When the plasma velocity is 150 km/s, the ion density increases in the shock layer in front of the tether, and then drops rapidly as the ions are repelled by the tether. The electron density tracks the ion density closely until the latter peaks and keeps rising as the electrons are attracted by the tether. At 550 km/s, the high kinetic energy of the ions moves

the shock front closer to the wire, and the electron density separates earlier than for the other two cases.

2.4 Langmuir probe general theory for laboratory testing

Langmuir probes (LPs) have been developed in the 1920s by Langmuir and Mott-Smith, and they are employed to acquire many plasma properties such as electron temperature, density, plasma potential, and electric energy distribution. They are generally very easy to design and operate, and usually they consist of a wire charged at a certain potential immersed into plasma and the acquisition of the current, in order to derive the V vs I curve.

The charged probe will be surrounded by a sheath made of electrons and ions, depending if the probe is charged positively or negatively.

Lobbia and Beal [10] stated some assumptions necessary for the applicability of the standard theory:

- Thermal equilibrium (Maxwellian velocity distribution);
- Collisionless plasma ($Kn \gg 1$);
- Absence of magnetic field ($\lambda_{lar} \gg r_{probe}$) and electrostatic ($\frac{d}{dt} = 0$);
- Quasi-neutral plasma;
- Plasma isotropic and homogeneous, absence of plasma drift.

In the presented current calculations, it will also be assumed that $\lambda_D \ll r_{probe}$. This will enable all the charged particles that enter the sheath to be collected, and holds true for laboratory testing conditions.

In order to calculate the total current that hits a probe, it may be convenient to estimate separately the contribution from electrons and ions. When the bias voltage is negative enough with respect to the plasma potential V_P the probe reaches the negative value of saturation current I_{is} . This value is negative since positive ions will be collected. For great values of V_B the ion current will reach the zero value since positive ions will not be hitting the probe anymore. For a Maxwellian distribution of current [9]:

$$\begin{cases} -I_{is} \exp[q(V_P - V_B)/k_b T_i], & V_B \geq V_P \\ -I_{is}, & V_B < V_P \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

the saturation current can be calculated:

$$I_{is} = \frac{1}{4} q n_i v_{th} A_{probe} \quad (2.11)$$

provided that the electron temperature is close to the ion temperature. A_{probe} will be the external surface of the cylinder. For a cold plasma, this expression is not valid and must be replaced with:

$$I_{is} = 0.6 q n_i \sqrt{\frac{k_b T_e}{m_i}} A_{probe} \quad (2.12)$$

where the thermal speed is given by:

$$v_{th} = \sqrt{8kT_i/\pi m_i} \quad (2.13)$$

For the electron current similar calculations can be performed:

$$\begin{cases} I_{es} \exp[-q(V_B - V_P)/k_b T_e], & V_B \leq V_P \\ I_{es}, & V_B > V_P \end{cases} \quad (2.14)$$

$$I_{es} = \frac{1}{4} q n_e v_{th} A_{probe} \quad (2.15)$$

the electron saturation current will be around 180 times greater than the ion saturation current as a consequence of the greater thermal velocity that comes from a lighter electron mass. The floating potential is reached when the contribution of electrons equals the one from ions and therefore no current passes through the wire. Generally speaking, this value is negative as a consequence of the fact that electrons are lighter and therefore easier to attract. For a cold plasma, this value can be derived by equalling the current to zero:

$$V_f = V_P + \frac{kT_e}{e} \ln \left(0.6 \sqrt{\frac{2\pi m_e}{m_i}} \right) \quad (2.16)$$

Figure 2.10: Typical V, I curve in a Langmuir probe. Once this curve is obtained, the plasma characteristics are computed [11].

stainless steel anode rods and a central copper cathode. The choice of using a rodded electrode configuration instead of a solid outer anode was for better optical access in the acceleration region. Since this arrangement was implemented, no significant changes to the performance of the plasma accelerator have been detected. The diameter of each electrode is 5 mm, and they are attached to two flanges that are connected to the rest of the power circuit. The flanges are insulated from one another with a high-density polyethylene insulator. The gun device is first evacuated to a vacuum level of 10^{-7} Torr

Figure 3.2: A picture illustrating the distinct parts of the "head" of the plasma gun that produces and speeds up hydromagnetic currents.

Figure 3.3: Photograph of the plasma jet.

in order to ensure reliable and repeatable operation. High-voltage capacitors are then charged with enough energy to break down and accelerate the neutral gas. The timing of the discharge process is managed by controlling the moment the capacitors are switched across the electrodes and when the gas is pushed into the accelerator. If the neutral mass is not added, a breakdown will not happen since the gun is on the low-pressure side of the Paschen minimum. The electric field ionizes the neutral gas as it accelerates in a vacuum, causing inward radial current flow towards the cathode (shown by blue arrows in Fig. 2.3). The copper cathode collects this current, which produces an azimuthal B-field. The $\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$ force created by this accelerates the quasi-neutral plasma to high velocities. This force remains the main source of axial acceleration until the field topology changes near the end of the electrodes. At this point, the behavior of the device is heavily dependent on the operating mode.

The gun section of the vacuum facility includes components such as a gas puff valve, gun "head", 4-way ConFlat (CF) cross, a Pfeiffer TPH 380 turbomolecular pump, and a thermocouple vacuum gauge. These components are designed to be connected together with o-rings to allow for sustained operation at vacuum (10^{-7} Torr) conditions. The acceleration volume of the gun is housed in a 6-foot-long Pyrex

Figure 3.4: Representation of the firing process for the gun.

glass tube with an ID of 6 inches and an 8 inches CF flange that connects to the primary vacuum chamber through a gate valve. This section of the experiment was designed to provide high levels of optical access for experiment investigations. The glass tube was manufactured by Allen Scientific Glass and is axially reversible with 6 different 4 inches of window ports distributed along its length. The Dynavac

Figure 3.5: An image of a vacuum tube that contains a plasma gun device is presented. To enable optical diagnostics, removable flat windows have been added.

Corporation constructed a large vacuum dump tank featuring two chambers that are connected with flanges. This "T" shaped connection was initially designed to restrict the amount of heat generated during a period of extended operation to the cryopumps.

The Kinney KDH-850 rotary piston pump with a KDH-KMBD booster package is utilized to supply a rough vacuum to the chamber and subsequently back up the turbomolecular pumps. This pump has the capability of delivering a pumping speed of 2500 cubic feet per minute (cfm), allowing the chamber and gun section to reach 170 mTorr in about 30 minutes. The pumping section of the chamber is connected to two Torrmaster 1200 (TMI-1200) cryopumps provided by Consolidated Vacuum Incorporated (VCI). The pumps in this system have a high pumping capacity, with the ability to pump 57000 liters per second of nitrogen (N₂) and 25000 liters per second of xenon (Xe). They utilize a multistage helium refrigeration cycle to cool the cryogenic panels to a temperature of 15 K, at which point the gas molecules adhere to the panels and are removed from the gaseous phase in the chamber. This process is aided by the use of two helium closed circuit scroll compressors and the application of liquid nitrogen from a polycold, which cools the baffling around the cryogenic panels and reduces their heat loading. The temperature of each panel is monitored using a Lakeshore Cryotechnic DT470 silicon diode sensor, which can measure temperatures as low as 1.4 K. During operation with hydrogen, a Pfeiffer TPH model 520 turbomolecular pump is also used to prevent saturation of the cryopumps.

The Stanford plasma gun is usually operated between 3 and 9 kV. In the experiments detailed in this dissertation, a single capacitor bank of 56 μ F is used to power the discharge, resulting in up to 2.3

Figure 3.6: Photo of the Stanford PPL vacuum chamber. [21]

Figure 3.7: Intersection between the plasma gun and vacuum chamber.

kJ of energy over a period of $20 - 40\mu\text{s}$ with peak currents of up to 100 kiloamperes. The waveforms of the discharge events follow an underdamped RLC circuit with a period of around 10 microseconds. The remaining parts of the discharge process are discussed in the following chapters. The figure below shows the waveforms of the gun experiment for varying levels of charging energy. A wideband Pearson

model 4997 current probe and a Tektronix P6015A high voltage probe with respective bandwidths of 87.5 MHz and 14 MHz are used to measure the operational current and voltage traces of the discharge events. The energy to charge the capacitors is provided by a TDK Lambda 500 A high voltage power supply, which is designed to quickly charge capacitor banks.

Figure 3.8: Typical current and voltage waveform of the Stanford plasma gun.

3.2 Operation Sequence of the plasma gun

Many electromagnetic thrusters are modeled with the snowplow theory. A luminous plasma front generates and propagates through the coaxial tube. This region is conductive and can be assimilated to a current sheet that sweeps and plow all of the downstream mass out of the acceleration volume. The temperature and the pressure of the current sheet tend to increase as it propagates and hits neutral particles: the higher the temperature, the more conductive the region is. This will drastically reduce the exhaust velocities and foster the electrode degradation rate.

The phenomena can be modeled using a RLC series circuit model:

$$V = IR + \frac{d}{dt}(LI) \quad (3.1)$$

where V is the capacitor voltage, I the total current, L and R the equivalent inductance and resistance. The circuit model can be related to the macroscopic flow properties:

$$m_s \frac{d^2 x}{dt^2} + \frac{dm_s}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} L'_G I^2 \quad (3.2)$$

where m_s is the mass of the current sheet and L'_G is the inductance per length of the gun. The expression $\frac{1}{2} L'_G I^2$ represents the Lorentz force of the accelerated current. In this model, the mass accumulation is not included (indeed \dot{m}_s).

Even with recent improvements that enable to account for the semi-permeable effects the predicted exhaust velocity is far from being accurate and the acceleration process observed experimentally is rather different for the Stanford plasma gun [1]; hence, the Rankine-Hugoniot model is a better option to describe the characterising phenomena of this experimental facility.

First of all, the puff valve is opened and neutral gas is pulled into the accelerator volume. The gas requires about $6\mu s$ to diffuse in the chamber once the valve is opened. The potential is applied in between the anode and cathode and this ionizes the gas. When the gas is finally ionized the breakdown happens and a quasi-steady deflagration wave is generated, that expands upstream towards the feed point while the gas is being accelerated. A pinch is generated at the endpoint, and it can be described very well by using the magnetic nozzle theory. When the current crosses the zero value the gun transitions to a detonation mode, considering that the presence of the gas will inhibit the expansion: the plasma is accelerated downstream anyway, because the angular magnetic field will reverse together

with the current. The wave will propagate toward the residual/partially ionized gases. The current will oscillate following the dynamics of an RLC circuit, and hence a sequence of damped deflagrations and detonations will occur. This will continue until there is sufficient current to support a discharge.

Figure 3.9: Sequence of phenomena in the gun accelerator.

3.3 Quad Langmuir probe for plasma measurements

The more we know regarding the accelerated plasma, the more effectively the test campaign will be planned. The density and temperature of both ions and electrons have important consequences on the preliminary estimations of thrust and current. To ensure repeatability, these quantities shall be acquired simultaneously and in a time resolution, without changing the probe applied potential [12]. To ensure these characteristics, considering the transient plasma discharges, a conventional single probe will not be adequate and therefore a quad probe will be required. A quad Langmuir probe doesn't rely on the characteristic curve I vs V but rather on the resolution of a system of 4 non-linear equations, it gives all the necessary data vs time.

Figure 3.10: An example of a circuit scheme for a quad probe. [13]

This kind of probe usually consists of four cylindrical electrodes: three of them are aligned with the plasma, the fourth is perpendicular, and this allows the determination of ion flow velocity, in addition to the thermal velocity that can be determined by the other probes. Usually one of the probes is floating (I_2 in this case) and two of them are charged at the same potential (I_4 and I_3 in this case).

Figure 3.11: Scheme of the QLP used in the Stanford Plasma Physics Lab mounted downstream the plasma gun. The horizontal distance from the gun can be varied.

Characteristics of the plasma state are determined by its density, electron temperature, ion Mach number (from which the ion velocity can be determined), and plasma potential. The probe used for this purpose is composed of four independent wires, each 4 mm long and $75\mu\text{m}$ in diameter. Probes 1, 2, and 4 are oriented in the direction of the flow, while probe 3 is placed perpendicularly to it. The currents collected by electrodes 2, 3, and 4 are monitored through wideband Pearson current monitors, and the current collected by electrode 1 is calculated through a current balance between the four electrodes.

3.4 Why the plasma gun as a solar wind simulator?

Figure 3.12: Photo of deflagration plasma jet source for e-sail studies.

The streaming plasma has the capacity to create plasma densities between 10^{13} and $10^{16} \frac{1}{\text{cm}^3}$, electron temperatures of 3-30 eV, and plasma velocities of up to $150 \frac{\text{km}}{\text{s}}$. This high ionization is beneficial, as it means that a positively charged wire will not cause a noteworthy ionization of neutral particles in its vicinity, a state that is expected in the solar wind in outer space. The plasma discharge is powered by a capacitor bank with a ring-down time of 5 – 20 μs , which can be adjusted by changing the inductance of the transmission line to the coaxial gun.

Figure 3.13: Experimental results for a run with the quad probe at 0.5 m from the gun. The used gas was Nitrogen and will be the same in the experimental test campaign for the e-sails.

Chapter 4

Current discharge experiment

The first phase of the experimental test campaign aims to address the following research question, mentioned before in Chapter 1: "Estimating the current discharged by a wire charged at a certain high potential to validate the respective PIC estimation. This value of current is fundamental to estimating the energy consumption of the propulsive unit, since the potential of the wires will be higher than the plasma potential, an emitter has to expel electrons in the real spacecraft, and therefore it will demand energy from the electric power generators. The secondary objective of this measurement will be the testing and characterizing of the dynamics of the test setup, which will be charged at a certain potential and tested in the subsequent experiment for current discharge measurements."

4.1 Characteristics of the accelerated plasma

The electric sails concept described before can be compared to an actual sail used for maritime applications: the structural parts are the metallic charged tethers and the fabric part is given by the plasma sheath that surrounds them. Therefore having a significant sheath radius that is at least larger than the wire diameter is a fundamental testing condition for measuring thrust and current. For the Stanford plasma gun, the plasma density is estimated to decrease longitudinally, starting from a value of 10^{22} at a distance of around 5cm from the pinch [1].

This value depends on the ionized gas that is pluffed in the valve. At 50 cm from the pinch, measurements of plasma characteristics have been conducted using the quad-probe described before, for Nitrogen and Hydrogen. All the currents of the probes are reported together with the discharge current of the capacitors bank. Velocity, potential, Mach number, and temperature reach the highest peak during the first strong deflagration, which will mostly contribute to the measurement of thrust and current conducted with this facility for the e-sails. The momentum flux is also reported, and can be calculated knowing the properties:

$$\frac{dF}{dS} = n * m_{proton} * V^2 + n * kb * Te \quad (4.1)$$

Cheng Gun Experiment. Gas: N_2 . Charging Voltage: 3.42 kV. Chamber Pressure: 10^{-5} Torr.

Figure 4.1: Plasma properties at 0.5 m from the pinch for the gas Nitrogen. The firing event lasts roughly $30\mu s$ and includes an initial deflagration that shapes the peak, followed by a detonation and another weaker deflagration.

Cheng Gun Experiment. Gas: H_2 . Charging Voltage: 3.03 kV. Chamber Pressure: 10^{-5} Torr.

Figure 4.2: Plasma properties at 0.5 m from the pinch for the gas Hydrogen. The density is noticeably smaller, while the ion velocity is greater since hydrogen is lighter than Nitrogen.

The peak momentum flux for hydrogen is about one-fourth of nitrogen. The plasma density is the most important governing parameter both for the thrust and current measurements.

Therefore, testing a surrogate device at the same distance from the pinch would not be convenient. Although the momentum flux would be higher, since the contribution of the dynamic pressure is more important than the sheath radius width, making the thrust measure easier, it would not be possible to scale the results since the structure of the plasma around the wires will be very different. Hence, it would be more convenient to further move downstream. At about 1 meter from the pinch the tube that contains the gun intersects the bigger vacuum chamber. At the very end of this tube, the density value is expected to decay approximately by 100 times with respect to the measurements of the quad probe at 0.5m from the pinch, and therefore they can be estimated as $3 \cdot 10^{19} \frac{1}{\text{m}^3}$ and $3 \cdot 10^{18} \frac{1}{\text{m}^3}$ for nitrogen and hydrogen respectively. The other physical quantities are expected not to vary significantly and may be assumed constant along the length of the tube. The actual values of density will be anyway measured and time-resolved as well as the other plasma properties inside the big chamber simultaneously with the current measures.

On top of that the vacuum chamber offers a test-bed that would allow for a more convenient integration of the components.

4.2 PIC simulations for current discharge event

PIC simulations have been run for a scaled design, more suitable for laboratory testing. For the gas Nitrogen, at $n = 3 \cdot 10^{19} \frac{1}{\text{m}^3}$, $T_e = 12\text{eV}$ a $50\mu\text{m}$ diameter wire charged at values of potential that are drastically below the spaceflight values. The simulation included an array of three wires distant 1mm each.

Figure 4.3: Ion density field around the charged tethers. The current gradient and force gradient show that even at a small distance of 1mm the interference results are minimal, especially for lower potential. The density structure is interesting since the peak density does not correspond to the center of the wire, as one would expect for non-plasma fluids.

The results for current are relatively high, as two wires of 10 cm of length each would lead to 66.6 A of current. For hydrogen lower values are expected, considering the lower density. Forces generated are on the other hand relatively weak, and this implies that in order to achieve a measurable value of

force an array with multiple wires is necessary.

4.3 Current discharge test design

The testing device is composed of metallic wires that directly interact with the accelerated plasma both for current collection or discharge purposes and are insulated from the ground with an acrylic frame. A rectangular duct will convoy the plasma from the long channel to the frame solidly mounted in the test bed of the big vacuum chamber. The frame is ample enough to allow for hosting the following testing configuration:

Two 10cm long, $50\mu\text{m}$ of diameter tungsten wires and the quad probe. Tungsten is selected to achieve the best durability. In this configuration, the two wires will be at a distance of 3 cm to avoid possible interference. The quad probe, located about 0.5 cm aside from the center, will be mounted on a vertical translation stage, and it will be capable of measuring the plasma properties along the mounting frame. One of the two wires will be centered with respect to the plasma gun, the other will be aside. The two values of current will be compared to account for any difference in density across the duct. Simultaneously, the quad probe will be recording plasma properties.

Figure 4.4: CAD representation of the plasma duct. All the quotes are in mm. The selected material is acrylic, laser cut.

Figure 4.5: CAD representation of the wires support. All the quotes are in mm. The selected material is acrylic, laser cut.

4.4 High voltage power box design

Ideally, to maintain the probes at high potential a high voltage source capable of delivering high current would be required, considering the current preliminary estimation mentioned previously. Such a device is certainly not available as simple laboratory equipment, and therefore a way to store electric power must be devised.

Capacitors offer the possibility of storing a discrete amount of energy, combined with a fast recharge. The energy required for maintaining the high voltage can be expressed as:

$$E_{capacitor} = N_{wires} t_{firing} I_{discharge} (V_{wires} - V_{plasma}) \quad (4.2)$$

the peak value of current will be considered as the worst-case scenario sizing the capacitor. The energy stored in a capacitor can be expressed:

$$E_{capacitor} = \frac{1}{2} CV^2 \quad (4.3)$$

where C is the capacitance value. If the current predictions are correct $16\mu\text{F}$ would suffice, although it would be advisable to pick a capacity that is at least 10 times greater than the computed one to assure a nearly constant voltage during the firing time. Additionally, if the same power box will be used for other experiments such as the thrust measurement, 4 mF of capacitance will be necessary. For the plate case, the expected current is even larger, requiring 650 J of energy for voltage keeping. Therefore, a capacitance of 10 mF is selected. For this category of capacitors maximum voltages are limited. Additionally, operating with hydrogen poses further risks related to arcing. Consequently, 250 V is chosen as a value of maximum voltage.

To control the circuit high voltage solid state relay are necessary, in order to avoid touching the circuit during operation. Once the capacitor is charged the voltage source is disconnected from the line. At the end of the operation, the capacitor must be discharged for safety reasons. A relay will connect it

to 4 discharge resistors connected to the ground line. A high-voltage diode is included in the design to prevent an incoming current due to the RLC circuit oscillations that can damage the capacitor. On top of that the components will be integrated in a metallic cage that will be grounded, in order to avoid EMC interference with the plasma accelerator.

Figure 4.6: Power circuit scheme. The relays are driven by a control switch box connected to a lower-voltage power source.

Figure 4.7: Photograph of the power box. Solid-state relays are selected to improve reliability. High-voltage cables are used together with insulation sheets to assure no discharge.

The power box output would be a cable that will be connected to the tungsten wires. The wires will therefore be charged at certain potentials and the discharged current will be measured using the Pearson probes.

Figure 4.8: Switch box for controlling the relays, one for charging and the other one for discharging the capacitors.

Figure 4.9: Photograph of the first configuration inside the vacuum chamber.

The Debye lengths for the predicted density is $5\mu\text{m}$ for Nitrogen, and it is somewhat connected to a more important parameter, the sheath radius. Estimations of this length are possible with Sanmartin et al. equation.

The two wires are fed through the walls of the chamber and each is crossed by a Pearson probe for measuring the time-resolved current.

Figure 4.10: Detail of a Pearson probe, that will be connected to an oscilloscope for measurement recording. The voltage output is directly proportional to the current across the wires.

The output of the experimental campaign will be the current for each wire, together with the plasma parameters, in function of time. The LC parameters of the circuit - i.e. the inductance, resistance, and capacitance- have been measured using a multimeter. Resistivity is expected to be low considering that electrical copper wires of gauge 10 are used, and it is therefore computed analytically. Having an accurate estimation of these quantities is fundamental for simulating correctly the equivalent circuit and then comparing the obtained current with the simulation results.

Figure 4.11: As the current source the power box presented before and a voltage source will be used. Once the relays are disconnected the power box reduces to an equivalent resistance, the diode, and the capacitor.

The potential of the wires is expected to vary during the firing time. The capacitor potential will be recorded during the firing time using a voltage probe.

4.5 Current Discharge Test Matrix

To address the objective of the first test campaign it is fundamental to assess the plasma properties across the duct. Across the pinch, the property distribution functions have been measured, and show significant variation. It is still unknown what would be the result downstream of the plasma duct. To address this question, the QLP is moved accordingly.

Datapoint	Gas	Voltage Wire [V]	Voltage Gun [kV]	Plenum pressure [psi]	Qlp Z [cm]	Source
1	N2	60	9	40	1	Capacitor
2	N2	80	9	40	1,5	Capacitor
3	N2	100	9	40	2	Capacitor
4	N2	150	9	40	2,5	Capacitor
5	N2	200	9	40	3	Capacitor
6	N2	220	9	40	3,5	Capacitor
1	N2	60	7	40	0,5	Power supply
2	N2	50	7	40	0,5	Power supply
3	N2	50	7	40	5	Power supply
4	N2	30	9	40	5	Power supply
5	N2	40	9	40	3	Power supply
8	N2	60	9	40	3	Power supply
9	N2	20	9	40	1,5	Power supply
10	N2	20	9	40	2,5	Power supply
11	N2	10	9	40	2,5	Power supply
12	N2	15	9	40	4,5	Power supply
13	N2	15	9	40	5,5	Power supply
14	N2	13	9	40	6,5	Power supply
15	N2	12	9	40	5,5	Power supply
16	N2	12	9	40	5,5	Power supply
17	N2	80	9	40	8,5	Capacitor
18	N2	70	9	40	7,5	Capacitor

Table 4.1: Current discharge test matrix.

Nitrogen is tested since it will be used for the thrust measurement campaign, considering the higher momentum flux delivered.

The stage will be moved vertically of 1cm large steps, starting from 1cm from the duct walls for a total of 9 data points across the duct, stopping again at 1 cm from the duct walls.

For each of these data points the plenum pressure of the puff valve and the gun charging voltage would be kept constant, and the current and voltage of the wires will be recorded. Reproducibility is a key issue for plasma accelerators. Each time the gun is fired at identical conditions the plasma characteristics may vary, and therefore each data point shall be repeated three times. The voltage of the gun capacitors is varied as well since it can regulate both the density and ion velocity. A higher charging voltage is expected to generate a denser and faster plasma, and for this purpose, 9kV and 7kV are both tested.

For some data, in particular, for lower voltages, a simple power supply is selected as a voltage source, and for V=60 V both the capacitor and the power source are confronted. Datapoints are eventually randomized to account for systematic error and biases caused by slight variations in environmental conditions and high voltage components.

Three oscilloscopes will be recording the quad probe data, the current of the wires, the voltage of the capacitor in the power box, and the capacitors bench data (current and voltage). The master

Figure 4.12: Characterization of the mass bit of the puff valve.

oscilloscope is triggered by the puff valve opening and it would eventually trigger the other two, to synchronize the data collection.

4.6 Current discharge test procedure

4.7 Gun Firing Procedure

To begin with, it is essential to take necessary measures to ensure the safety of the laboratory for the experiment, such as grounding capacitors, removing sensitive equipment, connecting cables and ground rods, testing the check relay, connecting the gas line, confirming setting gun, set up delay generator, install probe, check valve jam, set ignition slot, adjust the output voltage, remove short circuit cable and check relay switch.

The plasma gun is activated by first turning the relay to "CLOSE" for each capacitor bank that needs to be charged, and then connecting the valve's power output to the valve's capacitor for charging. After the valve capacitor reaches 900 V, it will be disconnected by the toggle switch. Then, the HV power supply's GND relay is set to the "CLOSE" position, and the HV power's HV's relay is to the "CLOSE" position, and the discharge resistor relay is to the "OPEN" position, while the power controller HV is switched to "Inhibit OFF" and "HV ON" mode. The power control knob should then be rotated slowly clockwise to allow the display voltage to rise and adjusted until the desired power supply voltage is reached. If the load voltage does not rise, the HV power supply controller is set to "ON" and "HV OFF", the discharge resistor relay is in the "CLOSE" position, and the HV power supply relay is in the "CLOSE" position. "OPEN". " position. After the display reads the desired load voltage, the HV power supply HV relay is set to the "OPEN" position, the HV power supply GND relay is in the "OPEN" position, and the HV power supply controller is in the "Prevent" position. block ON" and "HV OFF mode".

The valve spark gap switch controller is then turned on using the toggle switch, the white spark gap button pressed to puff the valve and initiate the gun firing, the valve spark gap switch controller turned off, and the dump resistor relay placed into the "CLOSED" position.

Once the test campaign is terminated the gun capacitors need to be discharged.

Caution should be exercised when being touched by components and the system should be assumed to be energized before servicing the circuit. The discharge resistance relay must be tested in the "CLOSE" state, the HV power supply should be in the "HV OFF" and "Inhibit ON" mode, and the voltage regulator knob should be rotated completely counter-clockwise. Switching relays and HV power should

be unplugged from the wall outlet; valve power must be disconnected from the valve capacitor by a toggle switch. The residual load must be discharged using the green knob on the discharge resistor, then the voltage and current knobs on the valve's HV supply must be rotated fully counterclockwise. The valve power supply should be turned off and short-circuited wires connected between the capacitor leads of the array(s) used in the test.

The voltage of the capacitor will be measured and recorded in time. Once the vacuum is created, a high-voltage source will be turned on and connected to the capacitor. Once the capacitor is charged the connection with the high voltage source is maintained till the triggering time for the discharge of the capacitors. The voltage in the capacitor would slowly drop when the connection with the power source is interrupted because of the internal losses and so it is very important to follow this rule. The capacitor will be disconnected from the power source to avoid overcurrents that could break fuses. Once the fire is terminated the capacitors will be discharged and then recharged for the following fire.

4.8 Test results

For each data point, three measurements are conducted, in order to compute the mean and the standard deviation for each single signal. The signal coming from the oscilloscope includes digital noise that leads to fluctuations of the signal, that are at high frequency and low amplitude. The filter applied averages the data points and reduces the total number to half the square root of the original number. The recording time for the oscilloscope is varied between $120\mu\text{s}$ and $240\mu\text{s}$ to fully capture the discharge.

Figure 4.13: Plot of the current collected by the central wire vs time. The wires are wet by plasma during a time of $30\mu\text{s}$. The shaded blue area represents the standard deviation, while the solid blue line is the mean between each shot. The first peak represents a plasma deflagration, while the second is a detonation.

Figure 4.14: When the voltage is increased the current increases as well. The two peaks are still clearly visible from the plot.

Figure 4.15: Comparison between different charge values for the gun capacitors. For higher voltages, the plasma density slightly increases and this leads to greater currents. The plasma velocity is visibly larger for higher charging voltages and it is in the order of tens of kilometers per second.

Figure 4.16: Comparison of the central wire current between several charging potentials and sources of current. The level of current as expected is influenced by the impedance of the power box, resulting average greater for the case of the simple power source.

Figure 4.24: As expected the voltage of the capacitor drops during the firing time because of the incoming electrons.

Figure 4.17: Besides the different maximum amplitude of current the electron collection time varies with different voltages, and in particular wires at lower voltages are capable to capture slower electrons.

Figure 4.18: Central wire charged at various voltages. The same time effect is shown here, the capacitor box is used as a power source this time.

The plasma properties can be considered uniform along the wire with good approximation. This can be seen in the quad probe data that was moved across the duct to scan the properties. The temporary voltage drop of the capacitor is, in large part, caused by the current flow. However the voltage, at the end of the firing, does not rise and this is not compatible with the amount of electron charge in the order of 3mC . It is still unclear what exactly happened but it is possible that one of the wires shorted with the vacuum chamber bed because of the plasma, that is grounded. Such a short would have occurred outside the recording time (and indeed no extremely high level of current is registered during the recording time).

(a) High voltage charge, confront between the two wires.

(b) Lower voltages. The result suggests that the plasma properties are pretty uniform across the duct.

Figure 4.20: Peak current vs charging potential of the wires. The peak current increases less than linearly, reaching a peak of 42A for the highest voltage.

4.9 Current Discharge Test Improvements

In order to address the potential drop issue, the experimental setup has been modified. The plasma duct has been removed since it ended up blocking many particles, and another translation degree of freedom is added to the system, in order to change the distance between the chamber aperture and the frame. This will allow us not just to get further from the wall of the vacuum chamber to avoid short circuits but will give us more insight regarding the plasma density decay in distance. A step motor controls this degree of freedom similar to the one that controls the height of the quad probe.

Figure 4.21: Total electron charge collected by the capacitor as a result of current integrated over time.

(a) Current of each wire probe of the QLP and gun capacitor, for Nitrogen 7kV.

(b) Plasma density during the firing time. The values are greater than predicted for the gas Nitrogen.

Figure 4.25: Photograph of the revised version of the experimental test setup.

(a) Plasma potential during the firing time. Peaks represent deflagration and detonation.

(b) Electron temperature during the firing time. Even in this case deflagration and detonation are visible.

4.9.1 Test Matrix

As in the previous test campaign, the applied voltage in the wires is varied to assess the electron collection capability. The QLP is positioned in the same relative position as in the previous test campaign in order to avoid to have interference between the long wires and the probe wires. The QLP is moved in four different positions to check the plasma property variation along the wires. The frame together with the probe is moved backward of 5cm to assess the property variation. The capacitors are kept at 3kV, to compensate for the absence of the duct that was actually blocking many particles, therefore, reducing the density. To obtain the average and the standard deviation three measurements are repeated for each data point.

Datapoint	Gas	Voltage Wire [V]	Voltage Gun [kV]	Plenum pressure [psi]	Qlp Z [cm]	Aperture distance [cm]
1	N2	60	3	40	1	17
2	N2	80	3	40	2	22
3	N2	100	3	40	3	22
4	N2	150	3	40	4	22

Table 4.2: Test matrix for the improved device.

4.10 Test Results

Figure 4.26: Current for the highest voltage of the campaign. Interesting to notice that the density is indeed greater, even if the charging voltage was reduced to 3kV and the distance from the aperture was increased. The resulting plasma density appears to be greater and the wires are able to suck more electrons at higher voltages.

Again, if the height of QLP is varied the plasma properties appear to be uniform. Even when moving to the horizontal stage, the plasma density seems to be approximately constant, suggesting that the length scale in which variations are expected is probably in the order of meters rather than centimeters.

Figure 4.27: The increase of the peak current with higher voltage this time appears to be greater since the duct was blocking many electrons.

Figure 4.28: Total electron charge collected by the capacitor as a result of current integrated over time.

Figure 4.29: The voltage appears to be stepping down as soon as the electrons are coming, and then later it increases as expected, suggesting that the issue of the final short circuit is fixed if the frame is further from the walls of the vacuum chamber.

Chapter 5

Impulse measurement experiment

5.1 High sensitivity pendulum design

5.1.1 Overview of the thrust measurement strategy

Thrust measurements require high sensitivity considering the weak force and the short firing time. For a wire, charged at a voltage value of the power box, namely 500 V, at the peak estimated density of $3 \cdot 10^{19}$ for the nitrogen gas inside the big vacuum chamber the expected gradient force calculated via PIC is $75 \mu\text{N}/\text{cm}$. This grows with the voltage and with the plasma density. The sheath thickness is as well increasing voltage and density, and it determines what is the sphere of influence of each singular wire. It can be noticed from the PIC simulations result that the interference of the potential structure of an array of multiple wires, each of them at 1 mm of distance is minimal in the final value of the force gradient. For a higher potential than 500 V, this is generally not true.

The estimated impulse for 50 wires, each of them 10cm long, if the density function is approximated using a square function of $3 \cdot 10^{19}$ with 10s of amplitude, would be $0.375 \mu\text{Ns}$. It is a rather low value and designing a device suited for this precise measurement can be really challenging.

The typical thrust stand configuration for pulsed plasma thruster is the classical pendulum schematizable with an equivalent spring, mass, and damper, as reported by Haag et. all [23]. Measuring the deflection right after a fire would allow us to determine the angular impulse IL delivered by the thruster to the pendulum using the following expression, derived from the mechanical energy conservation:

$$IL = \frac{\theta_r k_s}{\omega_n} \quad (5.1)$$

where θ_r is the angular deflection, k_s the torsional stiffness spring, ω_n the natural pulsation of the system. The torsional stiffness depends on the construction material of the arm and on the flexural pivot. The advantage of using a flexural pivot is the absence of static friction since there are no slipping surfaces, and it is a great advantage for small impulse measurements. The damping comes in large part from the internal damping of the steel. The torsional stiffness of the system can be calculated with an excellent approximation via FEM analysis, by applying a virtual load of 1 N at the lower extremity of the pendulum. The torsional stiffness then would be:

$$k_s = \frac{1 \cdot L^2}{x} \quad (5.2)$$

where L is the length of the pendulum and x the maximum displacement. In general, knowing the amplitude of the pendulum deflection at a certain point, defined as a point of measurement, it is possible to estimate the impulse of the force applied at the point of application:

$$I = \frac{A_{pmeas} k_s}{\omega_n L_{pmeas} L_{papp}} \quad (5.3)$$

Figure 5.1: Example of the flexural pivot, manufactured by Riverhawk. The spring stiffness is generated by the vertical flanges and no slip occurs.

where A stands for the amplitude of the initial oscillations.

To effectively test a charged rectangular-like shape a frame is needed. This frame has as well to be mechanically connected to the flexural pivot, and the static inclination shall be adjustable in order to ease the laser alignment. The selected material for the pendulum is the stereolithography resin

Figure 5.2: CAD representation of the pendulum frame. All the quotes are in mm. The grooves allow for obtaining a harp-like structure when the frame will be used for measuring the wire thrust. A number of 50 wires is selected to obtain a measurable impulse without mutual interference between two wires. Each wire is about 11cm long, although the wet length is 10 cm because of the plasma duct.

SIRAYA Tech Fast, considering the relatively low cost of this technique and the high manufacturing precision combined with excellent resistance to vacuum.

Considering the low estimated impulse, a high-sensitivity measurement technique for the pendulum deflections is needed; laser interferometry appears to be an excellent candidate for the purpose.

Figure 5.3: 3D CAD representation of the frame.

Knowing the deflection of the pendulum, the impulse can be estimated very easily with the expression derived before. However, there are other factors that have been neglected in that approximation, such as the internal damping of the materials. The best practice, in this case, is to devise a calibration strategy that allows the derivation of the impulse vs deflection line. The selected solution is a voice coil with a magnet. The magnet will be glued in the bottom support of the frame together with the mirror that will reflect the laser beam.

5.2 Insights on laser interferometry for distance measurement

A Michelson-type laser interferometer is used to measure distance by comparing the phase difference of two parts of the same beam. One part is sent to the reflector at a known distance and the other part is sent to the measuring surface at an unknown distance. When the two signals recombine in the interferometer, the resulting phase is related to the distance from the interferometer to the reflecting surface. Therefore, the phase of the combined signal changes as the distance changes. These methods have the advantage of being highly accurate while allowing long-range measurements. However, as the accuracy requirements of various applications have increased, interferometers have been tuned to be less susceptible to various influences. A laser beam is split into two beams of equal intensity by a beam splitter. These beams are reflected by the end mirrors and recombined at the beam splitter. The amount of light detected is determined by the relative phase of the two beams. When in phase, they combine constructively and add the full intensity of the first laser beam to the detector. On the other hand, if the rays are out of phase, they combine destructively and no light is detected. By shifting the position of one of the end mirrors, small changes due to different light intensities on the detector can be measured. Laser interferometry is an accurate method for measuring small displacements and is a non-contact method that can be used over long distances. To understand interferometers in more detail, we need to delve into the mathematics. Approximating a Gaussian laser beam as a plane wave, the electric field of the propagating light wave can be expressed as:

$$E(z, t) = E_0 e^{i(-kz)} \quad (5.4)$$

where the amplitude E_0 is constant, $\omega = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the light frequency, $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the wave number, and λ is the light wavelength [18].

The laser typically used for this application is the Helium-Neon laser, which has a wavelength of 632.93nm, and therefore the oscillation frequency will be around $4.7 \cdot 10^{14}$ Hz. Instead of using an electronic device that is capable of operating at THz, detecting the beams by measuring the intensity would be more convenient:

$$I_0 = C(E_0)^2 \quad (5.5)$$

where C is a constant. Typically, for class R laser pointers, this value lies between 1 and 2 mW. A photodiode generates a current proportional to the intensity of the beam, and it is therefore preferred for this scope.

A 50:50 beam splitter is the first point of contact of the laser light, after which it is split into two

Figure 5.4: Optical scheme of the interferometry experiment used for measuring the deflections of the pendulum inside the vacuum chamber. L_1 and L_2 are the distances between the target and the beam splitter and reference and beamsplitter respectively. [19]

beams of equal intensity. These rays pass through the interferometer arm, where they are reflected by two mirrors. The beams are recombined at the beam splitter, with some of the light going to the detector and the rest back to the source. The intensity of the two beams is determined by the difference between the optical path lengths L_1 - L_2 of the two arms of the interferometer.

The sum of the two electric fields of the overlapped beam can be derived analytically:

$$E_{photodiode}(l_1, l_2) \sim \left[\frac{E_0}{2} e^{-ikL_1} + \frac{E_0}{2} e^{-ikL_2} \right] \quad (5.6)$$

that after some manipulation becomes:

$$E_{photodiode} \sim \frac{E_0}{2} [1 + e^{-ik\Delta l}] \quad (5.7)$$

where $\Delta l = l_2 - l_1$ is the difference between the two path lengths. The Intensity is correlated with the square of the electric field:

$$I_{photodiode} \sim |E_{photodiode}|^2 \sim \frac{E_0^2}{4} [2 + 2\cos(k\Delta l)] \quad (5.8)$$

And further inspection reveals the dependence on the differential path length:

$$I_{photodiode} = \frac{I_0}{2} [1 + \cos(k\Delta l)] \quad (5.9)$$

Therefore, by directly recording the overlapped beam intensity the deflection of the pendulum can be measured.

Figure 5.5: Typical plot of the intensity function. By counting the fringes and multiplying this quantity by half the wavelength, the differential distance can be calculated.[18]

The sensitivity of this setup corresponds to half the wavelength since the optical folding parameter is 2. In this particular case distances one of the targets is at around 1.5m of distance from the beam splitter and therefore a frequency stabilized laser is selected, since the typical coherence length of HeNe laser is around 20 cm, and it would be pivotal to obtain well-defined fringes.[20]

Figure 5.6: Typical fringes distribution. When Δl changes the fringes would translate. It is therefore fundamental to use a photodiode that has a detector diameter smaller than the width of the fringe.

The selected laser model is the Thorlabs HRS015B, which is also polarized. The frequency stabilization is achieved after about 20 minutes of operation, since the laser has to warm up. Interferometry is an extremely precise measurement technique and extremely sensitive as well. In order to achieve reliable measurements all the components must be mounted in a solid optical table and then the laser is aligned. The alignment phase is relatively critical since the beams have to be overlapped as much as possible. Optical surfaces are also very delicate and cannot be handled without gloves. The used laser is classified R and therefore no risks for eye exposure are generated. If the two arms of the laser are unequal, then combining the two beams will not eliminate the laser fluctuations. This is because the laser jitter experiences different time delays in the two arms and they cannot be canceled at the photodetector. [22]. Therefore is necessary to achieve the same arm distance.

5.2.1 Selection of the flexural pivot and FEM analysis results

The torsional stiffness of the flexural pivot is a crucial parameter for the pendulum design. In the case of a very hard pivot, the impulse will generate deflections that are below the sensitivity threshold for the interferometry setup. On the other hand, a weak pivot will lead to very high deflection and the two beams will not recombine when they reach the photodiode.

The dynamic response of the pendulum can be described using the classical harmonic oscillator equation:

$$J \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} + c \frac{d\theta}{dt} + k_t \theta + mgL_{xg} \sin(\theta) = F(t)L_{papp} \quad (5.10)$$

where θ is the angular deflection and c is the internal damping of the structure. Considering that for the thrust measurement, it would be important to measure the first deflection right after the gun firing the internal damping is not accounted for in the calculation. The conservation of the mechanical energy would give more insights about the calculation of the maximum deflection:

$$mgh + \frac{1}{2}mV_{xg}^2 = constant \quad (5.11)$$

that can be further expanded in :

$$(mgh_0 + \frac{1}{2}mV_{xg}^2) - (mgh_1 + \frac{1}{2}k_t\theta^2) = 0 \quad (5.12)$$

the difference in gravitational potential energy can be expressed as:

$$h_0 - h_1 = L_{xg}(\cos(\theta) - 1) \quad (5.13)$$

which considering the small deflections will reduce to:

$$L_{xg}(\cos(\theta) - 1) \simeq -\frac{L_{xg}\theta^2}{2} \quad (5.14)$$

As a result of the impulsive shot, the resulting angular impulse can be derived:

$$mV_{xg}L_{xg} = IL_{papp} \quad (5.15)$$

the resulting peak deflection is derived by assembling all the equations reported above:

$$\theta_{max} = \frac{IL_{papp}}{L_{xg}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{m(L_{xcm}mg + k_t)}} \quad (5.16)$$

and once estimated the deflection of the mirror support can be derived as well. The laser beam that hits the mirror is reflected back with an angle equal to double of the pendulum deflection. The resulting beam that recombines at the photodiode will be shifted of:

$$\delta = 2\sin(\theta)D_{arm} \quad (5.17)$$

where D_{arm} is the distance between the beamsplitter and the pendulum mirror, measured as 1.5m. The selected pivot is the 5006-400 model from Riverhawk. The expected deflection together with the modal frequencies can be preliminary estimated with FEM simulations. The vibrational modes that lead to a horizontal translation of the mirror are hereby reported. The values of the deformation vector are magnified for optimizing the visualization.

(a) Deflection of the pendulum in the bottom support.

(b) Result of the reflected incident laser beam vertical shift.

Figure 5.8: The pendulum will be approximated using the following scheme.

Figure 5.10: Bode plot frequency response of the structure.

(a) Detail of the deformation relative to the first frequency.

(b) Detail of the deformation relative to the fourth frequency.

Once the frequency response and the vibration modes are computed, it is possible to compute the response of the pendulum structure to an impulsive force. An example could be an impulse of $1\mu\text{Ns}$ applied to the bottom support of the pendulum. The impulsive load mostly excites the first

Figure 5.11: Force applied vs time in the frame. The total impulse is about $1\mu\text{Ns}$.

modal frequency, and the small higher frequency fluctuations are the second mode that does not affect significantly the pendulum deflection. The results of the fem analysis are coherent with the one degree of freedom calculations.

Figure 5.12: Horizontal displacement correspondent to the mirror location in the bottom support of the frame. The main resulting frequency is 2.882 Hz.

5.3 Insights on the calibration technique

A coil connected to a voltage source generates a magnetic dipole that is proportional to the current that crosses it.

$$m_{vc} = NiA \quad (5.18)$$

where A is the area of the coil. Knowing the magnetic dipole moment of the magnet the mutual force can be expressed as a function of the distance and the current:

$$F = -\frac{3\mu_0 m_{vc} m_m}{2\pi r^4} \quad (5.19)$$

which considers the magnet located exactly at the center of the voicecoil. The magnetic dipole of the magnet can be as well calculated:

$$m_m = \frac{V \cdot B_r}{\mu_0} \quad (5.20)$$

where V is the volume, B_r is the residual magnetization.

The selected voicecoil and magnet have the following characteristics: **Woofers Voice Coil Dual Layers Round Copper Wire**

Diameter [mm]	25.5
Height [mm]	11
Inductance [mH]	0.334
Resistance [Ohm]	8.31

B641 Magnet from KJ

Brmax [Gauss]	13200
Dimensions [inch]	3/8 x 1/4 x 1/16
Material	NdFeB, Grade N42

The assembled circuit follows the classical equation for RL circuits:

$$V_{dg}(t) - (R_{vc} + R_{dg})I - L\frac{dI}{dt} = 0 \quad (5.21)$$

where V_{dg} is the voltage delivered by the delay generator and $R_{dg}=50$ Ohm the internal resistance of the delay generator.

The actual value of force exerted on a magnet can vary significantly from the computed one. A correc-

Figure 5.13: Knowing the voltage function, the resulting force can be calculated using a Simulink model.

tion parameter that depends on the distance can be estimated experimentally by measuring the actual force, using a high-precision scale. For $r=2\text{mm}$ the correction factor $C=0.1921$. This consideration is

Figure 5.14: Characterization of the correction factor for the voice-coil. This value vary with the distance and has to multiply the force expression.

valid if the duration of the applied voltage square shot is much greater than the constant $\tau = \frac{L}{R}$. This value is around $5.6\mu\text{s}$, and therefore if the impulse width is larger the steady-state approximation is valid for the estimation of the correction coefficient.

By changing the voltage and the width different impulses can be delivered to the pendulum. Three impulses will be applied to the pendulum, $0.5 I_0$, I_0 , and $2I_0$, where I_0 is the estimated impulse delivered by the plasma to the pendulum by the accelerated plasma. Considering that the voice-coil is applying an impulse at the bottom of the pendulum, while the plasma will act at the center of the frame, the difference in terms of the lever arm has to be corrected, and in particular, the voice coil has to apply a lower impulse multiplied by the factor $\frac{L_{\text{center}}}{L_{\text{papp}}}$ where L stands for the distance between these points and the rotational axis.

Figure 5.15: Plot of the applied force for a magnet distant 2mm from the voice-coil. For a voltage equal to 2V and a width of 0.5 ms, the resulting impulse is around $0.5\mu\text{Ns}$.

5.4 Thrust measurement device integration

The pendulum frame shall include a permanent magnet for calibration and a mirror for laser reflection. It should be possible to disassemble the pendulum from the support of the flexural pivot, and regulate the inclination to ease the laser alignment.

Figure 5.16: 3D printed frame photograph. A square mirror is glued in the bottom support to reflect the incident laser beam. On the other side the permanent magnet for calibration.

Figure 5.17: Photograph of the assembled pendulum. The voice coil delivers an impulse and pushes the pendulum backward.

(a) Photograph of the pendulum adjustable support.

(b) Photograph of the voice coil adjustable support.

Having adjustable supports eases the positioning of the pendulum inside the chamber together with the laser alignment. Three layers of mechanical vibration insulation rubber are added to the corner of the pendulum platform to reduce the mechanical noise. The voice coil will be driven by a delay generator, that is capable of delivering an impulsive square shot, with the possibility to adjust the amplitude and the width.

Figure 5.19: Delay generator Berkeley Nucleonics 555

Figure 5.20: Photograph of the flexural pivot installation. The current will pass across the vertical screw to the bearing and then it will end up in the horizontal screw.

Figure 5.21: Preliminary interferometry setup mounted in a separate optical table.

A preliminary setup was mounted on the optical table of the small lab. The distance measurement has been validated by using the micrometer to change the distance of the reference mirror and then compare it against the computed distance.

Figure 5.22: Pendulum frame integrated inside the vacuum chamber.

Inside the vacuum chamber, the plasma is conveyed by the plasma duct to the frame area. The plasma duct is smaller than the frame, to make sure that the ions will not be hitting the frame borders. The pendulum is connected to the test bed with the adhesive insulation sheet layer to insulate the pendulum from the mechanical vibrations of the table of the vacuum chamber.

Figure 5.23: Schematic representation of the optical setup. The necessity of a 45-degree inclined mirror comes from the fact that in order to obtain fringes when the two laser beams recombine at the photodiode the arm distance shall be as equal as possible. A beam expander is necessary to increase the cross-section of the laser beam and improve the stability of the system.

Figure 5.24: Photograph of the optical table aside from the vacuum chamber.

The laser beam enters the vacuum chamber from the lateral window, hits the mirror of the pendulum, and then crosses back the window, the beam splitter, and finally the photodiode, where it combines with the beam reflected by the reference mirror.

The basement of both the voice coil and the pendulum are made out of acrylic, to insulate the metallic structure from the vacuum chamber bed, which is grounded.

5.4.1 Preliminary testing and code filtration procedure

A preliminary test to validate the laser interferometry setup was conducted, before proceeding with the calibration and the actual test. A free pendulum, without any wire, is mounted inside the vacuum chamber. The objective of the test is to verify that the structure vibrates at the expected natural frequency. Considering the preliminary nature of the test, no vacuum is created inside the chamber.

Figure 5.25: Detail of big Pearson probe used for current measurement, higher current levels are expected.

Figure 5.26: Detail of the final pendulum that includes the 50 tungsten wires. Each of them is connected to a copper rod that provides connectivity with the power box. Silver conductive paint is applied to enhance the conductivity.

The laser is aligned following the scheme presented before in this chapter. The two beams must overlap to achieve the fringes, and for this purpose, a long painstaking sequence is followed, in which all the mirrors of the setup are rotated by tenths of degrees, the long distances make the assignment challenging.

Once the alignment is completed it is necessary to wait until the laser is warm enough to have an effective frequency stabilization. At this point, fringes are obtained. The pendulum is very gently displaced with a screwdriver and the signal is immediately recorded, with a time frame of 600 ms.

The photodiode is hit by the two beams and it records a varying voltage, depending on the intensity of the beams. Anyway, the signal is very noisy and needs to be filtered to properly count the fringes. From the power spectrum analysis, knowing the sampling frequency of the oscilloscope, a butter-worth low-pass filter of the second order is applied to the signal. Afterward, a further filtering stage is applied which averages the data points and reduces the total number to half the square root of the original

Figure 5.27: Photograph of the obtained fringes. The laser beam is not well collimated for this model and therefore it expands drastically with distance increasing.

Figure 5.28: Plot of the frequency spectrum. From this plot is it possible to understand the main source of noise and isolate consequently the actual signal.

number. Is it possible to notice that the frequency of the signal is not constant. Indeed, when the lowest frequency is reached it means that the pendulum reached the maximum amplitude and stopped. Each stop point is clearly visible from the voltage plot and is entered manually in the following part of the code, which would simply count the fringes, and add or subtract $\frac{\lambda}{2}$ for each fringe counted depending if it is before or after a stop point. The result is a sinusoidal displacement in function of time, as expected. The amplitude is expected to be in the order of microns even for the actual firing. The only important mode of vibration is the first, as predicted for the frequency response analysis.

Figure 5.29: Fringes output of the photodiode.

Figure 5.30: The actual frequency can be estimated in the order of 2.9 Hz, obtaining a deviation of 0.6 % from the computed one (2.882 Hz).

5.5 Thrust measurement test matrix

Datapoint	Gas	Voltage wires [V]	Voltage Gun [kV]	Plenum pressure [psi]
0	N2	//	//	10
1	N2	100	9	10
4	H2	//	//	5
5	H2	100	3	5
6	H2	200	3	5

Table 5.1: Impulse measurement test matrix

The mass bit of the puff valve is as well a key parameter since at the low end, it could potentially starve the plasma leading to ablation and erosion of parts of the gun and introducing new particles into the plasma. Additionally, it changes the time it takes for enough pressure to be built up to lead to a breakdown. This could change the location of the ionization wave and lead to a slightly slower plasma jet and probably lower densities. The mass bit can be controlled by variations in the plenum pressure of the valve.

As mentioned before, the 'fire' of the gun is composed of highly ionized plasma at the very beginning followed by neutral gas. The final momentum delivered to the pendulum will be from both those phenomena, and therefore in the test matrix that impulse component must be estimated. Both nitrogen and hydrogen are tested at several potentials, also for the gun capacitors. The resulting current discharge will be recorded together with the potential of the e-sail power box capacitor.

5.6 Thrust measurement procedure

First of all the pendulum support is fixed to the vacuum chamber bed using the adhesive insulation sheet. Four squares 0.5×0.5 cm, each of them $3/8$ inch thick are applied to the corners of the rectangular basement. The calibration voice coil is screwed into the vacuum chamber bed and connected to the delay generator using the feed troughs. The voice coil must stand at a distance of 2mm with respect to the magnet. At this point the pendulum is mounted before starting the shooting phase, calibration should be the priority. The objective of this phase is to derive a curve impulse vs deflection, and this is achieved by delivering 4 impulses that are close to the predicted value of impulse for the gas nitrogen charged at 9kV. Each of these measurements is repeated 2 times and the results are averaged in a linear regression. As stated before the result is expected to be a straight line.

At the end of the calibration phase, the delay generator is disconnected from the voice coil, to avoid to risk of damage from the current generated by the plasma.

Then the gun is fired and the oscilloscope connected to the photodiode is triggered together with the others. As done in the previous runs, for each data point three measurements are collected. The support and electrical connection are verified with a multimeter.

The second phase of the setup preparation is the laser alignment, which can take an extensive amount of time to be completed. The laser beam must go through the beam splitter, then the vacuum chamber window hit the pendulum mirror, bounce back to the beam splitter, and then overlap with the other beam coming from the reference mirrors. Once the fringes are achieved in the photodiode, the oscilloscope must be adjusted to optimize the output reading, and ultimately the total acquisition time shall be set to 600 ms to capture at least two complete oscillations of the pendulum.

Once the alignment phase is completed, vacuum is created inside the chamber. In this phase, abrupt maneuvers with the valves shall be avoided as much as possible since they may result in pendulum misalignment. Turbopumps will be preferred over cryopumps to minimize the mechanical noise, at the price of a higher background pressure in the order of mTorr.

5.6.1 Calibration

Once the vacuum is created and the laser properly aligned, the calibration is the next step, right before starting the testing campaign. The relation between impulse and deflection is linear as shown before, and therefore the best option is to collect three impulse measurements. Each of these points is collected twice for calculating the average.

5.7 Post processing and test results

As reported in the test matrix, firstly three shots with just the pure gas are performed. Between one shot and the other, it is necessary to wait that the turbopumps to bring the pressure back to mTorr

Figure 5.31: Comparison between the calibration and the predicted curve. The linear fit of the calibration shows slightly lower deflections because the 1 DOF model does not account for real effects like friction and damping.

levels, and this may require 15-20 minutes. Considering that the impulse result is very close in both

Figure 5.32: Pendulum deflection after a shot of nitrogen. The impulse is estimated to be in the order of $150\mu\text{Ns}$, far more than what is expected both for the wire case and the plate case.

cases and indeed the effect of the gas alone largely predominates, another technique for estimating the impulse of the whole plasma is devised.

Figure 5.33: Pendulum deflection after a shot of nitrogen, with the wire array charged at 100V. The impulse is clearly very close to the one of the pure gas.

5.8 Test Improvements and final results

The new computation strategy is based on the fact that the plasma moves at very high velocities, estimated in the previous campaign with the QLP to be in the order of $40 - 50 \frac{\text{km}}{\text{s}}$, and therefore it would reach the wires much earlier than the neutrals. To identify the time range in which plasma occurs, the value of current is measured.

Figure 5.34: Current collected by the whole array of 50 wires. The current for each wire is about 160A, and is greater than the values obtained before. The charged structure seems to be capable of collecting slower electrons as well. The triggering time for this measurement is the valve opening, and therefore the time starts accounts for the gas expanding in the valve orifice as well.

Knowing the time window in which plasma occurs, fringes are counted and the final velocity is calculated. For some data points unfortunately data have been corrupted by the EMC noise. The velocity of the pendulum is directly connected to the impulse as stated in the following equation, which exploits the conservation of the angular momentum:

$$IL_{papp} = J\omega_{pendulum} \quad (5.22)$$

where p_{app} is the point of application of the impulse that ideally would be the center of the rectangular frame.

The angular velocity of the pendulum can be calculated from the mirror velocity:

$$\omega_{pendulum} = \frac{V_{mirror}}{L_{mirror}} \quad (5.23)$$

and so on the total moment of inertia:

$$J_{tot} = J_{pendulum} + m_{mirror}L_{mirror}^2 \quad (5.24)$$

Figure 5.35: The voltage is as well recorded and shows that with such a high level of current in the order of kA, the voltage drop is significant during the firing time.

The plasma duct turned out not to be so much effective in preventing the frame from being hit by particles. Therefore the pendulum was brought further to reduce the effect of the gas alone, and a plate was used for the same scope of the duct instead since it was deemed to be more effective.

Figure 5.36: Photograph of the improved test setup. To compensate for the distance variation the reference mirror of the interferometer has been moved as well to fulfill the requirement of the equal distance arms. A beam expander was also added to the optical setup to improve the beam overlapping making it easier to count the fringes with post-processing.

Figure 5.37: Only the first fringes are counted for computing the final impulse.

Figure 5.38: Plot of the filtered fringes. The instant in which the plasma is leaving the frame is called the point of interest and can be inferred from the current plot.

Figure 5.39: The overall displacement can be calculated once the fringes are counted.

The main source of error for this set of measurements is the sensitivity of the interferometer, which is about 316 nm. From the absolute error, the relative error can be computed and will be used for the error propagation in the following calculations.

Figure 5.40: The instantaneous velocity is computed from the displacement plot. The resulting instantaneous velocity in the point of interest will be used later for the impulse estimation.

Figure 5.41: The obtained impulse is greater than expected since the plasma density is greater, and quantifiable in the order of 10^{20} rather than $10^{19} \frac{1}{\text{m}^3}$. If the voltage increases the impulse increases as well, and the highest values occur for nitrogen, considering the higher density.

Chapter 6

Conclusion and future work

6.1 Overview of the achieved results

The experimental test campaign was mostly aimed to provide experimental data to validate the particle in cell code that will then be used for calculating the actual thrust of the e-sails in realistic spaceflight conditions that would be pretty hard and expensive to reproduce in an experimental environment. The Stanford plasma accelerator not only is capable of providing plasma at a high ionization degree, but intrinsically at high density, and then it is easier to measure current, because the signal stands out easily from the background noise, and eventually it is possible to measure the impulse, although with more uncertainty mostly because of the neutral gases coming after the plasma detonation.

The wires were capable of collecting a noticeable amount of electrons, despite being just $50\mu\text{m}$ in diameter each. The tungsten turned out to be a solid choice, for the levels of current. However, the first test campaign may have encountered a short circuit problem after the gunshot that dropped significantly the voltage of the capacitor. The issue was fixed by increasing the distance with respect to the vacuum chamber walls. The signal is however clearly affected by electromagnetic noise, especially the voltage measurements, with visible fluctuations.

For the impulse measurements, the pendulum was revised many times and it took an extensive amount of time and trials to obtain the right sensitivity. Interferometry was not the only option being considered. Strain gauges have been employed several times to measure a displacement that was the result of a resistance that can vary with different levels of strain. This option was ultimately discarded because it would require a hard material such as titanium for building the support of these strain gauges, which would be therefore very complicated and expensive in the short amount of time available for this thesis project.

The main source of error in the distance measurement and consequently in the velocity is the sensitivity of the interferometric setup. Additional sources of error come from the vibrations of the reference mirrors that would cause fringes if the amplitude exceeds the $\frac{\lambda}{2}$ of sensitivity. Cryopumps are not usable for this experimental setup - even if the quality of the plasma would be better with lower background pressures- because of the mechanical noise that would excite the pendulum.

6.2 Future work and feasibility

The sensitivity of the interferometry setup could be improved by further reflecting the laser beam on the target mirror and therefore increasing the optical folder parameter [19] to at least 4 or 8 in order to improve the sensitivity.

A piezo device could be connected to the reference mirror, and if it vibrates at high frequencies in the order of kHz with an amplitude that is less than $\frac{\lambda}{2}$ we would be sure that the fringes are generated by just the pendulum oscillating.

Each bmc cable should ultimately be covered with aluminum foil or equivalent to insulate the data from electromagnetic noise.

As a future expansion of the experiment, more charging voltages of the wires shall be tested. The valve could be ultimately modified to reduce the amount of neutral gas introduced, although a faster valve would decrease the plenum pressure and therefore the mass bit of the whole gun. Instead of using metallic conductive paint, it would be more convenient to solder the tungsten wires to the support copper bar to achieve a more durable design over time.

The e-sail project is just at the very beginning of its development. With the challenge of thrust and power consumption estimation, comes the structural development of such large tethers and deploys mechanism, a guidance navigation and control system that takes into account the solar wind and the space weather, plus the challenge of keeping those wires at the high potential in space with just using an electron emitter.

A smaller demonstrative mission is expected from NASA MSFC to be proposed in the next decade, to gain more practical insights on this fascinating yet very intricate technology.

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